

Electrochemical Sensors for Soil Health Monitoring

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Abstract:

Soil health using sensors is growing field to monitor and manage soil Conditions has emerged as a promising approach to develop advanced sensors for rapid, continuous monitoring of soil health parameters. The recent advancements in sensors for soil health assessment, their working principles, applications, the potential of various nanomaterials, in fabricating highly sensitive, selective for soil health monitoring, promoting sustainable agriculture. Electrochemical sensing system detecting one or multiple soil component effectively, efficiently, and selectively for soil quality and soil health care. There is a global interest on development of cost-efficient and fast analysis to soil quality. The electrochemical soil sensors are widely used to soil nutrients due to their cost-effectiveness, long-term deploy ability, fast response and multiplexing.

Keywords: *Electrochemical Method, Nanotechnology; Soil Quality, Soil Health, Soil Sensors, Sustainable Agriculture.*

Introduction:

Soil Quality is the ability of soil to perform specific functions, such as nutrient retention, water infiltration, and carbon sequestration [1]. Soil is a vital natural resource that supports plant growth, nutrient cycling, water regulation, and biodiversity [2]. Nanotechnology involves the manipulation of matter at the nanoscale (1-100 nm), where materials exhibit unique physical, chemical, and biological properties [3]. Nano technology-based sensors offer several advantages as real-time monitoring, high spatial resolution, low power consumption, and the ability to integrate with wireless communication technologies [4] The global agricultural demand is expanding speedily because of enhancing population and food production, and income growth through worldwide[5]. There is a global interest on development of cost-efficient and fast analysis to

soil quality. It is known that nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), and potassium (K) are the major macronutrients and iron, manganese, copper, zinc, boron, molybdenum, chlorine are the minor soil micronutrients[6]. These nutrients can essential elements plant growth and high product yields. Soil acidity or alkalinity is another important factor as it influences how easily plants can uptake nutrients from the soil[7-8]. The electrochemical soil sensors are widely used to soil nutrients due to their cost-effectiveness, long-term deploy ability, fast response and multiplexing. The electrochemical sensing have explored widely for point of use applications in many fields [9–13]. The schematic representations of electrochemical based sensor for Soil health monitoring are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig.1: Schematic representation of Electrochemical -based sensor for soil health monitoring.

Electrochemical Based Sensors for Soil Health Monitoring:

Nutrient sensing in soil using Electrochemical sensors: Nitrate, Phosphate High surface area and conductivity of graphene oxide for sensitive electrochemical detection.

pH Sensing in Soil using Electrochemical sensors: MoS₂ high surface area and electrocatalytic activity for pH sensing.

Greenhouse gas sensing in soil using Electrochemical sensors: N₂O Redox reactions at the electrode-electrolyte interface.

Challenges and Futures Prospects:

Despite the promising potential for soil health monitoring, These challenges include:

Interference from soil matrix: The presence of humic substances, clay minerals, and salts can affect the sensitivity, selectivity, and stability of Nano sensors with high specificity and robustness against soil matrix interference is crucial.

Biocompatibility and toxicity: The development of biocompatible and eco-friendly Nano sensors is essential to minimize their adverse effects on soil health.

Durability and long-term stability: The development of durable and stable Nano sensors with self-cleaning and self-healing capabilities is necessary for their long-term operation in soil.

Standardization and calibration: The development of standardized protocols and calibration methods for Nano sensors in different soil types is crucial for their accurate and reproducible measurements.

Cost and scalability: The development of cost effective and scalable manufacturing methods for Nano sensors is essential for their commercial viability and widespread use.

Future Prospects and Recommendations:

In electrochemical method, an ion-selective membrane (ISM) combined with electrochemical transducer is widely used for soil nutrients detection such as nitrate, potassium, phosphorus. conducting polymers can provide ionic to electronic conduction via the oxidation/reduction or doping/undoping mechanism. For potentiometric soil sensors, the contamination with non-specific ions and damaging of ISM can cause the sensor potential drift and signal instability.

Conclusion:

Electrochemical sensor made to fabricate miniaturized electrochemical sensing system for soil quality assessment Such of advancements will be useful to reduce farming cost, minimize excessive pesticides & fertilizer utilization, manage crop growth, and achieve quality food and Contribute to sustainable agriculture.

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